

Table 1. Comparison of insect pest and natural enemy abundance on insect-susceptible varieties in continuous and biannual cropping systems over a 2-year period. IRRI, 1978-79.

Year	Crop	Cropping system ^b	Whorl maggot ^c (grade) 30 DT	Stem borer ^d (%)		Leaf folder- ^e damaged leaves(%) 40-50 DT	Rice bug ^f (no./ 5 m ²)	Hoppers ^g (no./m ²)			Spiders ^g (no./m ²)	Egg parasitization ^h (%)		
				Dead- hearts 50-55 DT	White- heads			BPH ^h	WBPH ⁱ	GLW ^j		BPH ⁱ	WBPH ^j	GLH ^k
<i>IR1917</i>														
1978	First	Biannual	5	3.5	2.5	<1	<1	4.2	2.1	3.6	16	53	55	38
		Continuous	4	5.0	4.5	<1	<1	3.1	0.2	0.2	5	65	54	53
	Second	Biannual	5	7.0	6.5	4	3.0	0	0.1	2	10	10	5	5
		Continuous	6	8.5	8.0	5	4.5	0	0	1	11	10	11	3
<i>IET3877</i>														
1979	First	Biannual	3	2.5	0.5	<1	2.5	0.04	0.3	1	4	14	4	4
		Continuous	3	5.0	0.5	<1	2.5	1.3	0.3	0.6	9	7	6	4
	Second	Biannual	5	1.3	0.8	0.5	2.0	0.3	0.5	0.9	3	3	2	2
		Continuous	5	1.3	0.6	0.5	1.0	1.3	0.04	0.6	9	5	2	2

^aDT = days after transplanting. ^bUnreplicated treatments. Insects were monitored from the continuous cropped plot planted the same week as the biannual crop. ^cHydrellia sasakii: 1-9 scale based on damaged leaves: 1 = < 1%, 3 = 1-25%, 5 = 26-50%, 7 = > 50%, 9 = > 5% with tom leaves. ^dScirpophaga incertulas and Chilo suppressalis: 5-m² sample area. ^eCnaphalocrosis medinalis: 100-leaf sample. ^fLeptocoris oratorius: 5-m² sample taken in early morning. ^gMean of 6-7 weekly samplings (10 hills/sample) from FARMCOP suction machine. ^hMean of 64 weekly exposures of hopper eggs using Otake's method. ⁱNilaparvata lugens. ^jSogatella furcifera. ^kNephotettix virescens and N. nigropictus.

Table 2. Insect pest parasitization in continuous and biannual cropping systems.^a IRRI, 1978-79.

Year	Crop	Pest	Stage	Individuals held (no.)		Parasitization (%)	
				Biannual	Continuous	Biannual	Continuous
1978	Second	<i>L. oratorius</i>	Egg ^b	213	147	4	16
		<i>S. incertulas</i>	Larva	24	14	21	7
		<i>C. suppressalis</i>	Larva	24	5	8	60
		<i>C. medinalis</i>	Larva	60	73	33	29
1979	First	<i>S. incertulas</i>	Egg ^b	623	734	96	95

^aUnreplicated treatments. Parasitization was recorded from field plots in the continuous cropping system planted the same week as the biannual crop. ^bUsing Otake's exposure method.

tinuous plantings. The differences over seasons, however, were neither great nor highly consistent.

Natural enemies of hoppers — spiders and egg parasites — were abundant in both systems (Table 1). Spider numbers were greater than the combined populations of plant hoppers and leafhoppers. The differences in hopper egg parasitization between cropping systems were not striking.

Parasitization estimates of the other pests over the 2-year period were more difficult to make because the pest populations were generally low (Table 2). Parasitization estimates of leaf folder larvae and yellow stem borer eggs were almost identical in both systems. Parasitization of rice bug eggs was low, but was greater in continuous cropping. Conclusions regarding parasitization of

stem borer larvae were difficult to make because of the low sample sizes, but biannual cropping favored yellow stem borer parasites, whereas the continuous system favored striped stem borer parasites.

Evidence from 2 years' observations of insect-susceptible cultivars without insecticide supported hypothesis 2; continuous cropping did not dramatically increase or decrease insect pest populations. Based on economic thresholds used in 1978-79, no more than two insecticide applications would have been justified (1st and 2d crops of 1978) and the application number would have been the same for both cropping systems.

Three factors regarding extrapolation of these results should be borne in mind: 1. The plots used were small and perhaps the fields surrounding the trial,

which received high levels of insecticide, helped cause the low pest numbers;

2. The location of the experiment on the IRRI farm (itself-a continuously cropped field) may have increased the pest populations in the biannual plot; and

3. The conclusions are limited only to insect pests. ■

Agroeconomic comparison of farmers' rice cropping patterns in a Bangladesh village

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Rice is grown year-round and occupies more than 80% of the total cropped

area of Bangladesh. In about 18 basic cropping patterns, rice is grown as the major crop. Where irrigation is available, rice is preferred unless other crops such as wheat, potato, chili, are more advantageous. Under irrigated highland and medium highland situations, the most important cropping patterns are high yield (HYV) boro - HYV t. aman and HYV aus - HYV t. aman, but some farmers may grow a pattern of three rice crops or of a rice - rice - nonrice crop.

In 1978-79, detailed monitoring was done in 62 contiguous farmers' fields in a deep tube well irrigated area at the Salna cropping systems research site of BRRI. Daily record keeping on farmers' field operations and inputs used along with crop-cutting was done to determine input-output of cropping patterns on each plot. The boro crop was irrigated, and the aus and t. aman crops were mainly rainfed. Results indicated (see table) that annual rice production from a hectare of land could vary from 2.3 to 10.3, depending on cropping pattern. Among the single-crop patterns, the HYV boro crop gave the highest production (5 t/ha), net return, and benefit-cost ratio. Among the two-crop patterns, the highest annual production (7.4 t/ha) came from the HYV t. aman - pajam boro pattern, but the highest net return and benefit-cost ratio were from the pajam t. aman - local boro pattern. Among the three-crop patterns, the highest production, net return (\$1,324/ha), and benefit-cost ratio came from the HYV aus - pajam t. aman -

Average productivity, costs, and returns of farmers' rice cropping patterns, Salna rice cropping systems research site, BRRI, 1978-79.

Rice cropping pattern ^a	No. sampled	Total yield (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
HYV aus	1	2.3	205	120	1.6
Pajam t. aman ^b	3	3.2	141	423	4.3
Local t. aman	2	2.7	242	216	1.9
HYV boro	1	5.0	222	844	4.8
Local boro	1	2.9	235	420	2.8
HYV aus - local t. aman	3	5.5	328	532	2.6
HYV aus - pajam t. aman	2	5.4	268	564	3.1
HYV aus - pajam boro	2	5.9	362	746	3.1
Pajam t. aman - local boro	2	7.0	251	1069	5.3
Pajam t. aman - HYV boro	12	7.3	430	957	3.3
Pajam t. aman - pajam boro	12	6.5	378	927	3.4
HYV t. aman - pajam boro	4	7.4	567	948	2.6
Local aus - pajam t. aman - pajam boro	3	9.2	628	1114	2.8
HYV aus - local t. aman - HYV boro	1	7.6	442	890	3.0
HYV aus - pajam t. aman - local boro	2	9.5	470	1200	3.6
HYV aus - local t. aman - local boro	2	8.0	580	1026	2.8
Local aus - local t. aman - HYV boro	2	5.5	589	489	1.8
HYV aus - pajam t. aman - pajam boro	4	9.9	542	1293	3.4
HYV aus - pajam t. aman - HYV boro	3	10.3	480	1324	3.8

^a HYV = high yielding variety, t = transplanted. ^b Pajam is considered neither a HYV nor a local variety in official statements in Bangladesh.

HYV boro pattern, which also gave the highest production and net return among all the test patterns. The lowest production, net return, and benefit-cost ratio came from the single HYV aus crop. Interestingly the results indicated that the growing of a single HYV boro crop could give higher net return and benefit-cost ratio than those for some two-crop or even some three-crop patterns. Similarly, some two-crop patterns could also give higher

production, net returns, and benefit-cost ratio than some three-crop patterns. Net return and benefit-cost ratio were, of course, influenced by the cost of production and prevailing market price for different rice varieties. The results of the present study may explain why farmers, often called great economists, sometimes do not go for intensive cropping patterns despite irrigation and other facilities. ■

Residual nitrogen fertilizer in soil and its availability in a rice - wheat cropping system

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In a field experiment on a Vertisol, 80 kg N/ha was applied to rice in 3 split doses and to wheat in 2 splits using ¹⁵N-labeled urea. The rice crop used 18.6 kg N/ha, and wheat 22.4 kg (LSD 0.05 = 1.4). Kjeldahl analysis of soil samples

Residual nitrogen fertilizer and its availability. AICRIP, Hyderabad, India.

Crop	Season	Treatment ^a		LSD (0.05)
		Rice-wheat rotation	Wheat-rice rotation	
Rice	1977 wet	¹⁵ N	¹⁵ N	
Wheat	1977-78 dry	0 N	¹⁴ N	¹⁵ N
Rice	1978 wet		0 N	¹⁴ N
<i>Kg N/ha</i>				
Residual fertilizer N after 1st crop		21.0	18.4	N.S.
Uptake by 2d crop		1.3	0.4	0.1

^a¹⁵N = fertilized by labeled urea, ¹⁴N = fertilized with unlabeled urea, 0 N = no N fertilizer added, N.S. = not significant.

drawn from the root zone after harvest showed that the residual nitrogen after rice was 21 kg/ha, and that after wheat

18.4 kg (see table). The KC1-extractable labeled NH₄ + NO₃-N in the root zone amounted to 0.42% of the added nitro-